

Reframing Ambidexterity: A Systematic Review Integrating a Dynamic Multi-Level Framework

Systematic Literature Review Protocol

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1. Introduction

This document presents the research protocol guiding a systematic literature review on organisational ambidexterity. The review aims to synthesise and integrate structural, contextual, and sequential perspectives to identify mechanisms through which these forms are combined across organisational levels and over time.

The protocol defines the research questions, search strategy, eligibility criteria, screening procedures, data extraction framework, quality assessment approach, and synthesis methods. The review follows PRISMA 2020 reporting principles and adopts a qualitative thematic synthesis approach suitable for theory-building research in management.

The protocol reflects the procedures followed during the conduct of the review and was formalised to enhance methodological transparency, reproducibility, and alignment between the planning and reporting stages. It provides a structured foundation for understanding how integration logics contribute to dynamic, multi-level ambidexterity configurations.

2. Review Rationale and Objectives

Organisational ambidexterity has been extensively conceptualised through structural, contextual, and sequential approaches (Tushman & O'Reilly, 1996; Gibson & Birkinshaw, 2004; Raisch et al., 2009). While these perspectives have advanced theoretical clarity, the

literature remains fragmented regarding how these forms are combined and coordinated across organisational levels and over time.

Recent calls in ambidexterity research emphasise the need to move beyond typological comparisons toward integrative and processual understandings (Raisch & Birkinshaw, 2008; O'Reilly & Tushman, 2013). However, no systematic synthesis has comprehensively examined the mechanisms through which organisations blend different ambidexterity forms.

The purpose of this systematic literature review (SLR) is to synthesise existing empirical and conceptual studies in order to:

1. Map how structural, contextual, and sequential ambidexterity are conceptualised.
2. Identify recurring patterns for combining these forms.
3. Examine higher-order mechanisms enabling integration across organisational levels and temporal cycles.

The review will follow systematic review principles adapted for management research (Tranfield, Denyer & Smart, 2003; Kitchenham & Charters, 2007) and will be reported in alignment with PRISMA 2020 guidelines (Page et al., 2021). It uses qualitative thematic synthesis rather than statistical meta-analysis, due to methodological heterogeneity in the included studies.

3. Research Questions (RQ)

The review will address the following research questions:

RQ1. How are structural, contextual, and sequential ambidexterity conceptualised in the literature?

RQ2. What patterns exist for combining different ambidexterity types within organisations?

RQ3. What mechanisms enable integration of ambidexterity across organisational levels and over time?

4. Review Design

This review adopts a qualitative thematic synthesis approach to examine how structural, contextual, and sequential ambidexterity are conceptualised and combined across organisational contexts. The choice of a qualitative synthesis is informed by the conceptual heterogeneity of the ambidexterity literature, which includes qualitative case studies, survey-based empirical studies, and conceptual contributions. Given this diversity in research designs, theoretical framings, and operationalisations, statistical aggregation through meta-analysis would not be appropriate.

Specifically, the included studies are unlikely to report comparable effect sizes, and key constructs are operationalised in substantially different ways across contexts. Moreover, the objective of this review is theoretical integration rather than statistical generalisation. Accordingly, a qualitative synthesis allows for the identification of recurring integration

patterns and higher-order mechanisms that may not be reducible to quantitative effect estimates. This approach aligns with recommendations for theory-building systematic reviews in management research (Tranfield et al., 2003).

The review will proceed in three structured phases: planning, conducting, and reporting. The planning phase defines the research scope, questions, and inclusion criteria. Steps and definitions consolidated in this protocol. The conducting phase involves systematic search, screening, quality assessment, and data extraction. The reporting phase synthesises findings to address the research questions.

The unit of analysis is organisational ambidexterity configurations examined at the firm, business-unit, project, or multi-level organisational contexts. Studies focusing solely on individual-level cognitive constructs without organisational embedding will not be included.

5. Search Strategy

5.1 Databases

To ensure broad coverage of management and innovation scholarship, the following databases will be searched:

- Scopus
- Web of Science
- EBSCO
- ScienceDirect

These databases are selected for their extensive coverage of peer-reviewed journals in strategy, innovation, and organisational theory.

5.2 Search Terms

Search strings were developed iteratively to capture literature addressing ambidexterity and its integration. Pilot searches were conducted to compare keyword-based and phrase-based search strings. The phrase-based strings that demonstrated higher conceptual precision, were chosen to be adopted. Search syntax will be adapted to the requirements of each database, as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Search string for each database

Database	Search Fields Used	Adapted Search Syntax	Filters Applied	Notes / Rationale
Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY	TITLE-ABS-KEY((structural OR contextual OR sequential) AND (ambidexterity OR ambidextrous))	English; Article;	Scopus allows structured field search; used metadata only to increase precision

Web of Science Core Collection	TOPIC (Title, Abstract, Keywords)	TS=((structural OR contextual OR sequential) AND (ambidexterity OR ambidextrous))	English; Article;	TS includes title, abstract, author and keywords
EBSCO Business Source	Abstract OR Title	AB((structural OR contextual OR sequential) AND (ambidexterity OR ambidextrous))	Peer-reviewed; English	EBSCO syntax requires field prefix (AB, TI)
Science Direct	Title, Abstract, Keywords	(structural OR contextual OR sequential) AND (ambidexterity OR ambidextrous)	Research articles; Business, Management & Accounting	ScienceDirect does not allow complex field codes; limited metadata filtering

The search string prioritises conceptual precision over breadth; therefore, some studies using alternative terminology may be identified through snowballing.

5.3 Time Frame

No lower time boundary will be imposed in order to capture foundational and contemporary contributions. The final search will be executed from 19-21 May 2025. All records retrieved up to the end of April this year will be included.

6. Study Selection Criteria

6.1 Inclusion Criteria

Studies will be included if they:

- Are peer-reviewed journal articles.
- Are written in English.
- Explicitly examine structural, contextual, and/or sequential ambidexterity.
- Address mechanisms, coordination, combination, or dynamic interaction among ambidexterity types.
- Contribute conceptually or empirically to the research questions.

6.2 Exclusion Criteria

Studies will be excluded if they:

- Address exploration–exploitation without reference to ambidexterity typologies.
- Are editorials, book reviews, practitioner articles, or non-peer-reviewed sources.
- Lack sufficient methodological or theoretical transparency.
- Do not align with the integration focus of the research questions.

Duplicate records will be removed prior to screening.

7. Study Selection Process

The study selection process will follow PRISMA 2020 principles and proceed through sequential stages. First, records will be identified through systematic database searches and exported for duplicate removal.

Second, titles and abstracts will be screened to assess preliminary relevance. Where necessary, introductions and conclusions will be consulted to clarify study scope. Studies that pass this stage will undergo full-text assessment against the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Screening decisions will be guided strictly by these criteria to minimise selection bias. One reviewer will conduct the initial title and abstract screening. To enhance reliability, a second reviewer will independently screen a subset of records during a pilot phase to ensure consistent interpretation of eligibility criteria and coding categories. Any discrepancies will be resolved through discussion prior to proceeding with full screening.

Following full-text inclusion, one round of backward snowballing will be conducted using the final set of included studies as seed papers. Forward citation tracking may also be performed to identify influential follow-up studies and ensure comprehensive coverage of the field.

8. Quality Assessment

Given the methodological diversity expected in the ambidexterity literature, a qualitative appraisal approach will be adopted rather than a numerical risk-of-bias scoring instrument. This choice reflects the inclusion of both empirical and conceptual studies and aligns with qualitative systematic review practices in management research (Tranfield et al., 2003).

Studies will be assessed during full-text screening based on the following criteria:

- Clarity and coherence of research design (where applicable)
- Transparency of data sources and analytical procedures
- Analytical rigor and internal consistency
- Strength and clarity of theoretical grounding

Rather than applying a formal scoring scale, studies will be evaluated holistically against these criteria. Those lacking sufficient methodological transparency or theoretical relevance to the research questions will be excluded.

Given the interpretive nature of thematic synthesis, analytical decisions and inclusion judgments will be documented throughout the review process to enhance transparency and reduce interpretive bias.

9. Data Extraction

A pilot extraction of a subset of studies will be conducted to refine the coding template. All records will be exported into Microsoft Excel for duplicate removal, screening, and data

extraction. No automation or machine-learning screening tools will be used. Duplicate records will be identified using Excel sorting and matching functions based on title and author.

Data extraction will be conducted systematically and reviewed to ensure consistency. Extracted data will include bibliographic information (author, year, outlet), research design (classified as qualitative, quantitative, mixed-method, or conceptual), industry context, organisational level of analysis (individual, project, business unit, firm, or multi-level), ambidexterity type(s) examined, and mechanisms described for integration. Classification categories will be defined prior to full coding and refined during pilot extraction.

10. Data Synthesis

Data synthesis will follow a deductive thematic analysis approach. Predefined analytical categories (structural, contextual, and sequential ambidexterity) will guide initial coding. Through iterative comparison and abstraction, higher-order themes reflecting integration mechanisms will be developed.

Predefined analytical categories include “Structural ambidexterity”, “Contextual ambidexterity” and “Sequential ambidexterity”.

Through iterative comparison and abstraction, patterns will be identified and grouped into higher-order mechanisms. The synthesis aims to move from descriptive categorisation toward theoretical integration, potentially identifying multi-level, dynamic, or pragmatic coordination logics.

Conceptual and empirical studies will be synthesised jointly, while recognising their distinct contributions to theoretical integration.

11. Reporting

The findings of the review will be reported in a structured and transparent manner aligned with PRISMA 2020 reporting guidelines (Page et al., 2021). A PRISMA flow diagram will document the identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion stages of the review process.

Reporting will proceed in two substantive stages. First, a descriptive profile of the included studies will be presented to characterise publication trends, methodological designs, theoretical orientations, and contextual settings. This stage will provide transparency regarding the scope and distribution of the evidence base.

Second, a thematic synthesis will be developed to address the research questions. This synthesis will move beyond descriptive categorisation to identify recurring integration patterns and higher-order mechanisms that explain how ambidexterity configurations are combined across organisational levels and temporal cycles.

Tables and conceptual figures will be used to enhance analytical clarity, illustrate integration mechanisms, and support traceability between extracted data and synthesised findings.

Any deviations from this protocol that occur during the review process will be explicitly documented and justified in the final manuscript to ensure transparency.

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